

Supplementary file 8: digital droplet PCR assays

This document provides all technical information related to the digital droplet PCR TaqMan assays used to quantify CYP6BB2 copy number and to quantify the frequency of the Ile1011Met *kdr* mutation.

1. Quantification of CYP6BB2 copy number using ddPCR

1.1. Primers and probes

Gene	Accession number	Primer name	Primer sequence (5' to 3')
CYP4D39 (control)	AAEL007808	F_CYP4D39	AGTCCTGGAAGTTCTGCACG
		R_CYP4D39	AAGGCGACTTTCCGACGAAT
		CYP4D39(Hex)	[HEX] AAGGAGGCAAACCCCGATAA [BHQ1]
CYP6BB2	AAEL014893	F_CYP6BB2	AGTTCAAGGGCCGAGGATTG
		R_CYP6BB2	CGGATCCACGAAAATTCCGC
		CYP6BB2(Fam)	[6FAM] GCTGGTTATCGATCCGGAGA [BHQ1]

1.2. ddPCR reaction Mix

Reagent	Initial concentration	Volume (μl)
ddPCR Supermix for Probes (No dUTP)	2X	12.5
R_CYP6BB2	10 μM	1.125
F_CYP6BB2	10 μM	1.125
CYP6BB2*	10 μM	0.625
R_CYP4D39	10 μM	1.125
F_CYP4D39	10 μM	1.125
CYP4D39*	10 μM	0.625
RNAse-free water	-	2.39
Restriction enzyme XhoI	10 U/μL	0.25
rCutSmart buffer	10 X	0.11
gDNA	5 ng/μL	4
	TOTAL VOLUME	25

1.3. ddPCR conditions

Step	Temperature	Duration
1. Polymerase activation	95 °C	10 minutes
2. Denaturation	95 °C	10 seconds
3. Annealing + Extension	60 °C	45 seconds
4. Repeat (2. + 3.) X 39		
5. End	4 °C	5 minutes
6. Polymerase inactivation	90 °C	5 minutes
7. Post-PCR waiting time	4 °C	∞

2. Quantification of *kdrl* Ile1011Met allele frequency using ddPCR

2.1. Primers and probes

Gene	Allele	Primer name	Primer sequence (5' to 3')
Voltage-Gated Sodium Channel Para (AAEL023266)		F_I1011M	TCCAATTTACTTTTCAGTCAGC
		R_I1011M	TGCTTGTGGGTGACG
	1011_Iso (wild type)	1011Iso(Hex)	[HEX]CTAGATTTCCATCACTACGGTGG[BHQ1]
	1011_Met (mutated)	1011Met(Fam)	[6FAM]ACTAGATTTCCATCACTACGGT[BHQ1]

2.2. ddPCR Mix

	Initial concentration	Volume (μ l)
ddPCR Supermix for Probes (No dUTP)	2X	12.5
R_I1011M	10 μ M	1
F_I1011M	10 μ M	1
1011Iso(Hex)	10 μ M	0.25
1011Met(Fam)	10 μ M	0.25
RNAse-free water	-	5.64
Restriction enzyme XhoI	10 U/ μ L	0.25
rCutSmart buffer	10 X	0.11
gDNA	5 ng/ μ L	4
	TOTAL VOLUME	25

2.3. ddPCR conditions

Step	Temperature	Duration
1. Polymerase activation	95 °C	10 minutes
2. Denaturation	95 °C	10 seconds
3. Annealing + Extension	59 °C	45 seconds
4. Repeat (2. + 3) X 39		
5. End	4 °C	5 minutes
6. Polymerase inactivation	90 °C	5 minutes
7. Post-PCR waiting time	4 °C	∞

2.4. Scatterplots profiles obtained from the observed Iso1011Met genotypes

Y axis = Fam channel (Met allele), X axis = Hex channel (Ile allele)

The resistant allele is duplicated (Ile-Met). The Wild type allele is in single copy (Ile)

Grey: Ile-/Met- droplets, Blue: Ile-/Met+ droplets, Green: Ile+/Met- droplets, Orange: Ile+/Met+ droplets

